

Analysis of Sensitive and Specific Intervention Policies in an Efforts to Resuce Stunting

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Stunting is a condition where a child's height is shorter than their age, this condition is better known as failure to thrive in toddlers. The study of the success of implementing policies to overcome nutritional problems was carried out through specific and sensitive nutritional intervention efforts in an effort to reduce the number of stunting. This study aims to analyze specific and sensitive nutritional intervention efforts in an effort to reduce the number of stunting in the Bengkulu City Health Center.

MATERIALS/METHODS: This study uses qualitative and quantitative methods with an exploratory design. Qualitative methods to determine the causes of stunting and quantitative to determine the effect on stunting. The population of pregnant women and mothers of toddlers and an analysis of the effect of specific and sensitive nutritional interventions in an effort to reduce the number of stunting.

RESULTS: The results of the study showed that the distribution of infant birth weight tended to be below 3.5 kg. Specific and sensitive nutritional interventions, such as providing additional food (PMT), iron tablets (TTD), exclusive breastfeeding, and monitoring growth and development and immunization status, have not shown a significant relationship with the incidence of stunting ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, environmental factors such as drinking water sources, sanitation, and types of toilets do not have a significant effect on the nutritional status of toddlers. Constraints in program implementation were identified in the aspects of coordination between stakeholders, limited human resources, and budget.

CONCLUSION: specific and sensitive nutrition interventions in Bengkulu City have not been effective in reducing stunting rates in toddlers. Strengthening cross-sector coordination and optimizing resources is needed so that stunting control efforts can run more effectively

KEYWORDS: Specific interventions, sensitive interventions, stunting

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INTRODUCTION

Stunting is a condition where a child's height is shorter than children of the same age, this condition is better known as growth failure in toddlers. Stunting is a problem because it increases the risk of illness and death, suboptimal brain development has an impact on delayed motor development and stunted mental growth in children¹. Results of the Toddler Nutritional Status Study, the prevalence of stunting in 2019 (27.7%), 2021 (24.4%) and 2022 (21.6%). Meanwhile, in Bengkulu Province in 2022 the prevalence of stunting was 19.8% and Bengkulu City was 12.9%². Government policies

and stunting intervention programs have not been considered effective. One of the reasons why government policies and stunting intervention programs have not been effective is that they have not been maximally used as a common foundation for overcoming stunting. The TNP2K report (2017) found that ministries or institutions implemented programs individually without sufficient coordination. Specific nutrition and sensitive nutrition intervention programs related to design, coverage, quality and targets still need to be improved. Growth due to stunting that occurs at an early age can continue and is at risk of growing short in adolescence. Children who grow normally at

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an early age can experience growth faltering at the age of 4-6 years have a 14 times risk of growing short in pre-puberty³.

The study of the success of the implementation of policies to overcome nutritional problems was carried out through several methods including systematic reviews, quantitative research, semi-qualitative interviews and problem tree analysis. There are eight variables that are obstacles, namely: difficulty in coordinating, weak strategies, lack of interest from stakeholders, weak stakeholder networks, weak policies, collaborative structures that are not in line with that, limited human resources and budget availability are not guaranteed⁴.

The above phenomenon is interesting to study considering that the problem of stunting has quite serious impacts; among others, the short term is related to morbidity and mortality in infants/toddlers, the medium term is related to low intellectuality and cognitive abilities, and the long term is related to the quality of human resources and degenerative disease problems in adulthood. Problems: specific nutrition intervention efforts and sensitive nutrition in efforts to reduce the number of stunting are not optimal.

METHODS

The research design is a program evaluation design that uses a qualitative and quantitative method approach with an exploratory design. Qualitative methods to determine the causes of stunting and quantitative to determine the effect on stunting.

The population of pregnant women and mothers of toddlers and an analysis of the effect of specific nutrition interventions and sensitive nutrition in efforts to reduce the number of stunting.

The independent variables are the diet of mothers of toddlers, provision of Complementary Food for Breast Milk (MP ASI), knowledge, attitudes and behavior of mothers of toddlers, the role of cadres, nutrition workers, related stakeholders and the dependent variable is prevention and control of stunting (Specific and sensitive nutrition indicators). The relationship between factors related to prevention and control of stunting. Quantitative data were collected using a structured questionnaire distributed to mothers of toddlers in five Bengkulu City Health Centers selected by purposive sampling.

Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS software. Bivariate and multivariate analysis were carried out to identify factors related to stunting. Odds ratios and 95% confidence intervals were calculated to determine the strength of the relationship between variables

RESULTS

Birth weight of babies of breastfeeding mothers who were counseled during pregnancy

Birth weight of babies is one indicator of pregnancy outcomes, education for pregnant women is one way to prevent Low Birth Weight (LBW). Birth weight of babies of mothers who received counseling during pregnancy in Figure 1

Figure 1 Birth Weight of Babies from Mothers Who Received Counseling During Pregnancy

The highest infant weight was 3.0 kg, with a percentage of 15.5%, of the total population. In addition, infant weights of 2.9 kg and 3.5 kg also stood out with significant percentages, at 12.1% and 13.8%, respectively. Figure 1 shows that higher infant weights, such as above 4.0 kg, have a much lower frequency of occurrence, with each category in this range only accounting for about 1.7% of the total population. Overall, this graph provides insight into the distribution of infant birth weights in the population, indicating a higher tendency for birth weights below 3.5 kg.

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Interventions for stunted toddlers

Figure 2. Body weight before and after intervention in stunted toddlers

Figure 2. shows that before the intervention, the nutritional status of toddlers based on the BB/U index was mostly in the normal category (65%) and after the intervention, most were in the normal category (75%). During the intervention, there was a decrease of (10%) in very low body weight.

Analysis of specific and sensitive nutrition intervention policies at Bengkulu City Health Centers

The government has established various policies related to stunting control in Indonesia. The local government has prepared derivative policies from the central government. Each health center has made efforts to overcome stunting problems, several programs are designed to reduce and eliminate stunting problems. Here are some activities that have been implemented by the health service unit:

1. Specific nutrition intervention programs that have been implemented

Intervention programs that have been implemented in 5 health centers and the Bengkulu city health office: Provision of additional food for pregnant women with chronic energy deficiency, Provision of additional food for toddlers with malnutrition/malnutrition/stunting, Provision of iron tablets for adolescents and pregnant women, Promotion and education of

exclusive breastfeeding, Promotion and Counseling for Provision of Infant and Child Feeding (PMBA), Monitoring of toddler growth (weighing and measuring height), Calcium supplementation for pregnant women, Vitamin A capsule supplementation, Zinc supplementation for the treatment of diarrhea for children aged 0-59 months, Pregnancy Examination & Immunization, Integrated Management of Sick Toddlers..

2. Sensitive nutrition intervention programs that have been implemented

Sensitive intervention programs that have been implemented in five (health centers and the Bengkulu city health office. Provision of drinking water and sanitation, health services in the context of, health insurance services, Reproductive health counseling, Counseling for prevent, Counseling to like eating fish, Other health counseling. Sensitive nutrition intervention program for provision of Community-Based Drinking Water and Sanitation (PAMSIMAS).

Relationship between Specific Nutritional Interventions and the incidence of stunting

The relationship between Specific Nutritional Interventions and the incidence of stunting can be seen in table 1.

Table 1. Relationship between specific nutritional interventions and stunting incidence

Specific Nutrition Interventions	Nutritional status		Total	<i>p value</i>
	Very short	short		
Pregnant Women Chronic Energy Deficiency				
Yes	1	7	8	0.619
No	3	9	12	
Additional Food Provision for Pregnant Women				
Not Getting	4	11	15	0.530
Getting	0	5	5	
Getting Iron Tablets During Pregnancy				
Not Getting	2	14	16	0.162
Getting	2	2	4	
Number of Iron Tablets Consumed				
None	0	1	1	0.832
≥ 90 tablets	3	10	13	
< 90 tablets	1	5	6	
Exclusive Breastfeeding				
Yes	2	14	16	0.165

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No	2	2	4	
Age given complementary foods breast milk				
Appropriate	3	15	18	0.368
Not appropriate	1	1	2	
Child is malnourished				
Yes	4	8	12	0.117
No	0	8	8	
Get malnutrition treatment				
Yes	3	8	11	0.591
No	1	8	9	
Getting Additional Food for Malnutrition				
Yes	3	8	11	0.591
No.	1	8	9	
Monitoring of toddler falls				
Every month	3	11	14	
Once every 2 months	1	2	3	0.777
Once every 3 months	0	2	2	
Never	0	1	1	
Officer visits if not to the integrated health post				
Yes	0	5	5	
No	4	11	15	0.530
Toddler immunization				
Incomplete	4	16	20	0.216
Complete	4	16	20	

The results of the analysis showed that there was no specific nutritional intervention that had a statistically significant relationship with the incidence of stunting in toddlers ($p > 0.05$). This can be seen in several variables, such as the condition of pregnant women with chronic energy deficiency ($p = 0.619$), provision of additional food) during pregnancy ($p = 0.530$), and provision of iron tablets to pregnant women ($p = 0.162$). The number of iron tablets consumed also did not show a significant effect ($p = 0.832$).

Likewise, the provision of exclusive breastfeeding ($p = 0.165$) and the timeliness of providing MP-ASI ($p = 0.368$) did not show a significant relationship with the nutritional status of toddlers. In terms of post-natal care, both children who

experienced malnutrition ($p = 0.117$) and those who had received treatment or supplementary food for malnutrition ($p=0.591$) also did not show a significant relationship with the incidence of stunting.

Furthermore, interventions for monitoring toddler growth and development, both through routine monitoring ($p=0.777$) and visits by officers when the child is absent from the integrated health post ($p=0.530$), did not show a significant correlation. Similar findings were also found in the toddler immunization status ($p=0.216$).

The relationship between sensitive nutrition interventions and stunting incidence

Table 2. The relationship between sensitive nutrition interventions and stunting incidence

Sensitive Nutrition Interventions	Nutritional status		Total	p value
	Very short	short		
Drinking Water Source				
Water Gallons are drunk directly	2	7	9	0.640
Water Gallons are cooked	1	1	2	
Water from PDAM is boiled	0	1	1	
Water from wells is boiled	1	7	8	

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Drainage in the house				
Yes	0	1	1	1.000
No	4	15	19	
Type of toilet				
healthy	4	15	9	1.000
Unhealthy	0	1		

Based on table 2. the results of the statistical test obtained a p value > 0.05 for drinking water sources (p=0.640), home drainage (p=1.00) and type of toilet (p=1.00) which shows that there is no significant relationship between drinking water sources, home drainage and type of toilet with stunting nutritional status of toddlers.

DISCUSSION

Intervention for stunted toddlers

Figure 3. shows that before the intervention, the nutritional status of toddlers based on the BB/U index was mostly in the normal category (65%) and after the intervention, most were in the normal category (75%). During the intervention, there was a decrease of (10%) in the normal weight of toddlers. During the interview, it was found that toddlers who experienced weight loss were sick when the intervention was carried out. Toddler weight is influenced by several factors other than food intake, infectious diseases are also direct factors that affect toddler weight⁵. Infectious disorders can worsen nutritional problems by reducing food intake and depleting essential nutrients in the body, toddlers who are infected with infectious diseases will lose their appetite and consume less nutrients and will produce less energy than toddlers need, research by Furqan, stated that there was no relationship between infectious diseases and nutritional status of toddlers⁶.

This study is in line with research conducted by Farida and Ony on the relationship between infectious diseases and the nutritional status of toddlers, the study concluded that toddlers who are often sick are at greater risk of having poor nutritional status⁷. This study is in line with research conducted by Wati on the analysis of supplementary feeding programs on children's nutritional status, the study concluded that toddler nutrition is not only influenced by PMT, but also the activeness of mothers in posyandu activities so that they know more about how to maintain toddler nutrition so that it remains good⁸.

Policy

Policies for handling stunting at the primary health care level, such as health centers, generally focus more on specific nutritional interventions, such as providing supplementary food, iron tablets, promoting exclusive breastfeeding, and monitoring toddler growth. However, sensitive nutritional interventions that focus on environmental factors, such as improving sanitation, providing clean water, and utilizing healthy latrines, are still not a top priority in some areas⁹. In fact, several studies have shown that environmental factors play an important role in preventing stunting, so efforts to improve sanitation and clean living

behavior should be integrated into stunting reduction strategies at the health center level. Stunting management policies at the primary health service level, such as health centers, generally focus more on specific nutritional interventions, such as providing additional food, iron tablets, promoting exclusive breastfeeding, and monitoring toddler growth. However, sensitive nutritional interventions that focus on environmental factors, such as improving sanitation, providing clean water, and utilizing healthy latrines, are still not a top priority in some areas⁹. In fact, several studies have shown that environmental factors play an important role in preventing stunting, so efforts to improve sanitation and clean living behavior should be integrated into stunting reduction strategies at the health center level¹⁰.

Relationship between Specific Nutritional Interventions and Stunting Incidents

The results of the analysis showed that 8(eight) KEK mothers with stunted child nutritional status. Short birth length or stunting at birth has not been studied extensively. Most of the anthropometric indicators studied reflect the current nutritional status of the mother and not the nutritional status of the mother in the past, so it is necessary to consider the role of maternal nutritional intake in the past¹¹. The results of the analysis showed that 15 mothers who received PMT during pregnancy had toddlers with stunting nutritional status. Malnutrition during pregnancy will increase the risk of LBW and stunting at birth. The risk of stunting will increase two-fold compared to LBW significantly in mothers who have low birth weight¹². Stunting growth, especially stunting tends to occur in the first 1000 days of conception and a person's second birthday. Women's nutritional health, especially before and during pregnancy, is very important for good infant development¹³. Providing iron supplements to pregnant women is essential to prevent anemia during postpartum, low birth weight, and premature birth¹⁴. The results of the analysis showed that 16 mothers who did not receive iron tablets had toddlers with stunting nutritional status. Breastfeeding counseling is very important for pregnant women in preparation for breastfeeding and counseling during breastfeeding for the continuation of breastfeeding. The results of the analysis showed that 16 children with exclusive breastfeeding had stunting nutritional status. It was found that 8 mothers received counseling with very short children's nutritional status and 26 mothers with short children's nutritional status. The mother's confidence in her breastfeeding ability is very important for successful exclusive breastfeeding¹⁵. In addition, the support of the husband as the closest person can

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motivate and help the mother during the breastfeeding process is very important for successful breastfeeding¹⁶. Monitoring must continue to be carried out so that children who experience stunting can immediately receive treatment. Mothers should routinely take their babies and children to the integrated health post for growth and development monitoring¹⁷. The results of the analysis showed that 14 toddlers who underwent monthly growth and development monitoring had stunting nutritional status.

The relationship between sensitive nutrition interventions and stunting incidence

In general, drinking water sources and sanitation are associated with stunting incidence. Concentrations of As and Cd in drinking water sources are thought to have a significant relationship with stunting incidence in Bandung Regency¹⁸. A possible explanation for these findings is that the mountainous environment does not reflect the reliability and quantity of supply that may be influenced by other hygiene-related behaviors, including water storage and overall hygiene practices¹⁹.

The best quality sanitation plays an important role in the prevention and treatment of various diseases related to the environment²⁰. Other studies have shown a significantly higher probability of stunting in toddlers in lowland zones, coastal zones, and clean water sources from drilled wells, while a significantly lower probability is found in gallon drinking water, standard toilets, cement and pipe wastewater construction materials, managed solid waste, ventilation not all rooms, adequate lighting in the room, and the father's livelihood as a civil servant and entrepreneur. The severity of stunting in South Lampung Regency is influenced by ecological zones, sanitation performance, and father's livelihood²¹.

Although there are significant differences, the health sector (Nutrition) contributes 40% of the total impact, while other sectors also experience similar progress through interventions within and outside the health service sector. industry and health sectors. Improving maternal education, nutrition, care for the elderly and young children during childbirth/pregnancy are important factors in shaping change through sensitization strategies. A large-scale child stunting control plan involves several steps such as diagnosis, consultation with stakeholders, and implementation of direct and indirect nutritional interventions in both the medical and non-medical sectors

CONCLUSION

Various specific and sensitive nutrition interventions that have been implemented in Bengkulu City have not shown a significant impact on reducing stunting rates in toddlers. The main obstacles are still found in the aspects of coordination, limited human resources, and suboptimal budget support. Strengthening cross-sector collaboration, increasing the capacity of health workers, and allocating more adequate resources are expected to increase the effectiveness of the stunting reduction acceleration program. Active community

support and participation are also key in creating behavioral changes towards better child growth and development.

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